

First Law of Thermodynamics from Mechanics of Photon Absorption in a Moving Frame

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In this note, we try to argue that one may see the emergence of the first law of thermodynamics by viewing the mechanics of photon absorption in a moving frame. In such a case, dQ (heat absorption) is defined as the change in energy of a mass $m_0 g(v)$ (due to the photon absorption $g(v) dm_0$), where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ with no momentum change, while the work energy is the energy change due to the added momentum of the photon. Thus, strictly mechanics may yield the first law of thermodynamics. One may note that a photon “warms” an object and so associate the mechanical results with a thermodynamical picture. Here heat energy + work energy leads to an overall dE which transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

Rest Frame Scenario

Consider a photon with energy e (moving in the x direction for simplicity) being absorbed by a gas with energy E , where $E \gg e$. Then:

Conservation of energy: total energy = $E + e$ ((1a))

Conservation of momentum: $e = (E+e) v_1 g(v_1)$ where $g(v_1) = 1/\sqrt{1-v_1^2/c^2}$ ((1b))

If $E \gg e$, then $e \approx Ev_1$ with v_1 very small, so one may consider $v_1 \approx 0$.

In such a case, $dE = e$. One might call e heat energy, but it may equally be considered as the energy of the photon. (Note: The photon may be moving in any direction.)

Moving Frame Scenario

Consider a photon moving in any direction being absorbed by an object with energy $m_0 g(v)$. In the lab frame:

$e = \text{photon energy} = dm_0$ (where m_0 is rest mass) because $v_1 \approx 0$.

Thus, in the moving frame: $e g(v) = g(v) dm_0$ ((2)) (Lorentz transformation)

Next, consider dE (energy change of the $m_0 g(v)$ object) from two mechanical points of view. First, consider energy absorbed with no change in momentum. This is the concept of heat. Energy is absorbed with no mechanical work being done. Next, consider the change in energy dE due to the work done by the photon by changing the momentum of the object $m_0 g(v)$

Heat Energy

$dE(\text{heat}) = d(m_0 g(v))$ for an object moving at velocity v in some direction. ((3))

$dp/dt = F_{\text{external}} = 0$ for no mechanical external work. Thus:

$$0 = v d(m_0 g) + m_0 g dv \quad dg = dv g^3 \text{ and}$$

$$dE(\text{heat}) = g dm_0 + m_0 dg \text{ so } dE(\text{heat}) = g dm_0 (1-v) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one argues that $g(v) m_0$ changes due to the absorption of the photon and that v will change (due to internal not external forces) so that $dp/dt=0$. Momentum remains constant so no external work is done.

The photon (moving in any direction), however, has momentum and momentum conservation must be applied. A change in momentum of the $g(v) m_0$ object implies an external force. This suggests mechanical work due to the external force and this should give rise to work energy.

$$E = pc + m_0 c^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((5))$$

$$E dE = p dp \quad ((6)) \quad dE = \text{mechanical work change in energy}$$

$$dp = g dm_0 \quad (\text{because a photon has a } e = p(\text{photon}) c \text{ dispersion relation}).$$

$$p/E = v \text{ so: } dE(\text{work}) = -dW = v g dm_0 \quad ((6))$$

This is the change in energy due strictly to a change in momentum. ((4)) represents the change in energy due to the absorption of the photon with no change in momentum. Adding the two yields the equation:

$$dE(\text{total}) = dE(\text{energy absorption with no momentum change}) + dE(\text{due to momentum change})$$

$$= dQ - dW \quad \text{the first law of thermodynamics} \quad ((7))$$

$$= (g dm_0) (1-v) + v g dm_0 = g dm_0 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, overall total energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector, but in both the rest frame and the moving, one has the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = dQ - dW \quad \text{with } dQ \quad ((9))$$

representing energy absorption with no momentum change and $-dW$, energy change due to a momentum change, i.e. work done by an external force.

Thermodynamically, the photon should add both heat energy and momentum to the moving object.

If one were to arbitrarily associate $dQ=TdS$, then in the rest frame: $T'dS' = dmo$, but in the moving frame: $dQ = TdS = (g dmo) (1-v)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the absorption of a photon in a rest frame and a moving frame. In the lab frame, if the system energy $E \gg e$ (photon energy), there is basically an increase in energy of e . In the moving frame, v can be any value up to c (speed of light in a vacuum). We consider two mechanical parts of energy. First, we consider the absorption of $g(v) e$, where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ with no change in momentum. This means that $dp/dt = 0$ and there is no external force or work. This is like an increase in mass which slows the system down. This type of change in energy we call heat. The second piece of energy is calculated by considering the change in momentum due to the photon, i.e. the external force or work it imposes on the system, $-dW$. We call this change in energy, work. Thus, $dE \text{ total} = dQ -dW$. In other words, strictly mechanical considerations lead to the first law of thermodynamics. One knows that a photon, being absorbed, raises a system's temperature through experiment. We find that for this problem, $dQ = g(v) (dmo) (1-v)$ and $-dW = v dmo$. Thus, the two add to yield $g(v) dmo$ which is the fourth component of a Lorentz 4-vector.